

Terrazole as a nitrification inhibitor

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Laboratory experiments showed that 4 00 ppm Terrazole (5-ethoxy-3 [trichloromethyl] -1,2,4-thiadiazole) was as effective as 25 ppm N-Serve in retarding nitrification in rice soils. Hence the potential of Terrazole

to increase nitrogen-use efficiency of urea-nitrogen by rice plants was evaluated under field conditions. Urea containing various proportions of Terrazole was applied to field plots just before the rice variety Labelle was planted on a Beaumont clay soil.

Terrazole had no measurable effect on grain yield, nitrogen-use efficiency (see table), or phosphorus or potassium content of foliage. It affected (5% probability level) the percentage of

nitrogen content of the most recently matured leaf at panicle differentiation. The zero-Terrazole treatment showed the highest nitrogen percentage in the leaf tissue. The 0.61% Terrazole slightly reduced nitrogen content. Nevertheless, increasing Terrazole levels tended to increase the nitrogen, suggesting that levels substantially higher than 1.41% may increase the nitrogen content of the foliage.

The nitrogen-efficiency values for preplant-applied urea were lower by about 10 kg grain/kg N than those normally obtained when the urea application was split. The NH_4^+ and NO_3^- concentration in the soil after harvest was not affected by Terrazole rate.

The lack of effect of Terrazole on N-use efficiency under field conditions, compared with its effect in laboratory experiments, could be explained by these facts: (1) Terrazole rates were at least 50 times greater in the laboratory; and (2) although the laboratory experiments showed 100 ppm Terrazole to be most effective in inhibiting nitrification during the initial 30 days, the field experiments continued for about 120 days.

Effect of Terrazole-treated urea on Labelle rice, 1975 growing season, Beaumont, Texas, USA.

Nitrogen (kg N/ha)	Terrazole in urea (%)	Mean yield ^a (t/ha)	N (%) in leaf ^b	N-use efficiency (kg grain/kg N applied)
101	0	3.9	2.76	22
	0.61	3.6	2.54	19
	0.93	3.5	2.59	10
	1.41	4.0	2.66	23
134	0	4.1		20
	0.61	4.2		21
	0.93	4.5		21
	1.41	4.5		21
168	0	5.3		21
	0.61	5.1		20
	0.93	5.3		21
	1.41	5.3		22

^a LSD = 0.5.

^b % N in most recently matured leaf at panicle-differentiation growth stage.

Iron chlorosis in paddy nurseries

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In the uplands, the raised-bed nursery method is not suitable for producing healthy, sturdy, and uniform seedlings which are a prerequisite for getting high yields. The flat-bed method of nursery raising, in which the field remains submerged, is conducive to reduction of iron and its better availability to emerging seedlings, thus preventing iron chlorosis in the paddy nursery. In a comparison of raised-bed and flat-bed methods at the Punjab Agricultural University Farm, Ludhiana, (1) seedlings

in the flat beds were green and healthy, (2) seedlings in the raised bed were chlorotic, and (3) weeds were more prevalent in the raised bed.

Seedling samples were removed at weekly intervals from the beds and analyzed for concentration of iron. Paddy seedlings from raised beds contained less iron than those from flat beds (see fig.). The iron content in the final sample, when the nursery was ready for transplanting, was deficient in the raised-bed nursery and sufficient in the flat-bed nursery according to the limits fixed by Chapman (1966).

To check iron chlorosis, the nursery should be sown in flat beds and be kept submerged. If iron deficiency appears,

Effect of method of nursery raising on iron concentration (ppm) in paddy seedling.

0.5–1.0% neutralized iron sulfate spray should be used regularly according to recommendations.